

ETHNIC FORMATION AND ECONOMY OF THE PEOPLES OF
CENTRAL ASIA

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Annotation: This article provides information on the ethnic formation and economy of the peoples of Central Asia.

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Today, the restoration and development of national and spiritual values in the Republic, the deeper inculcation and deeper expression of the ideas of national ideology in the minds of our citizens, the growing interest of the peoples of Uzbekistan in their past and origin. In particular, the topicality of the ethnic history of the Uzbek people, its formation as a nation was comprehensively substantiated in the work of President IA Karimov "There is no future without historical memory" (1998). In this direction, our historians have been set vital tasks. In particular, as the head of our state said, "In our long history, no invaders have entered the borders of Movaraunnahr, and for many years, perhaps centuries, no other dynasty has ruled in our territory ... Qutayba, Genghis Khan came from Mongolia, the Russians came. But what about the people left? "In the conditions of extinction, did our nation survive, albeit with a number of losses? Let our scientists answer this question." It is known that many researchers have recognized that the issues of ethnogenesis or the history of the origin of any nation are closely linked with the achievements of historical science. However, in relation to other areas of history (archeology, ethnography, anthropology, etc.), the ethnogenesis of the Uzbek people still requires serious research. Ethnogenesis If we look at the history of issues of ethnic history, it is in the preparation of this topic used the newly published data of K.Sh.Shoniyazov. Some observations in this direction can be found in the works of ancient and

medieval authors and travelers, written in Greek, Chinese, Roman, Arabic, Iranian and Turkish. In their works, they emphasized the commonality of the appearance of the peoples, the closeness of some traditions and the similarity of the dialect. But they failed to reveal the root causes of these processes. Although the research of the early nineteenth and early twentieth centuries was relatively effective, it did not fully reveal the causes and nature of the similarities in the ethnic origins, cultures, and languages of the peoples.

The anthropologist T.Q. Khojayev suggests paying special attention to the following principles in the study of the ethnogenesis of each nation:

The history of the origin of a nation is a multifaceted process, which includes the culture and social structure of the nation, its biological characteristics, understanding of its place in society, language and identity;

to look at the question of ethnogenesis one-sidedly, not only by simplifying it, but also by taking into account all the components which have played a definite role in the history of the origin of this people;

ethnogenesis is a complex and lengthy process. Therefore, it is advisable to restore a process step by step.

Also, A.A. In one of his recent works on the ethnogenesis of the Uzbek people (2002), Askarov states that the study of the ethnogenesis and ethnic history of each nation requires the following theoretical and scientific methodological principles:

- First, in the study of ethnogenesis and ethnic history, the researcher must first determine when the ethnogenesis of the people being studied began. Because ethnos is formed only at a certain stage of development of human society. The starting point of ethnogenesis goes back to the "ancestors" of the ethnos who lived in ancient times. This process took place a millennium ago. It happened at the end of the second millennium.

- Secondly, ethnos is not a biological product, but a social phenomenon. It is an event of a certain stage of personal development. In the process of its formation, the ethnos, for some reason, a new ethnic layer is added to it. All the peoples of the earth are of multi-ethnic origin. Indeed, from the earliest stages of the ethnogenesis of the

Uzbek people, until its formation as a nation, in addition to the local (autochthonous) Sogdian-Khorezmian and ancient Turkic-speaking strata, which formed its basic structure, absorbed ethnic groups from around the world

- Thirdly, the study of the ethnic history of each nation requires that the process of formation of ethnic identity begin at an early stage. Because the emergence, development and transformation of ethnic unity into an ethnos is a whole historical process that has been going on since ancient times.-

Fourth. When dealing with the ethnic history of each nation, it is necessary to study not only the initial process of ethnic unity, but also its subsequent periods, its important ethnic features and characteristics.

- Fifth, a comprehensive approach to the study of ethnogenetic processes, ie the use of scientific advances related to ethnogenesis, provides an objective scientific solution to the problem. It is important to know the nature of the primary sources used in solving ethnogenesis problems. These sources include anthropology, archeology, ethnography,

written monuments, linguistics, epigraphy, etc. Only if the above principles are fully observed, it will be possible to reveal the ethnogenesis of some peoples from a scientific point of view. However, in Central Asia, especially in Uzbekistan, Before comprehensively covering the ethnic processes taking place in the past, it is expedient to conclude that the achievements in the field of science can be used by other specialists in the field. Archaeological excavations in recent years have provided important information about the material and spiritual culture of the ancient population, its way of life, household items, traditional economy, and more. This process became the basis for the collection and analysis of new anthropological data. The process of ethnogenesis begins with the history of the ancestors of different peoples. The history of the ancestors of the Uzbek people covers a very long historical period. On the path of long historical development, our ancestors have gone through complex processes of ethnogenesis. These processes are inextricably linked with the intermingling of anthropological images of tribes, peoples and nations, the development of cultural traditions on a new basis. We know from

historical literature that this It was founded in ancient Greece 2-2.5 thousand years ago. That is why in modern science there are many words from the Greek language. Such words can also be found in the sciences of nations. The ancient Greeks had a few words to describe the concept of "people". One of them is "demos", which means the main part of the population (for example, "democracy" - "people's power", "demography" - "definition of peoples", etc.). Another such word is "ethnos", which literally means "people". According to the results of ethnographic research, any ethnos in the early stages of its formation consists of a community of people who are economically interconnected. One of the important distinguishing features of some ethnoses is their cultural characteristics. Each nation acquires these features in the process of its historical and cultural development and passes them from generation to generation. In science, this process is called "ethnic traditions." Such traditions are formed in one or another historical period, which is associated with the socio-economic and natural geographical conditions of each nation. In short, an ethnos is an organized linguistic and cultural community. The word "ethnic community" is also widely used in the scientific literature. Not only individual peoples, but also groups with which they are related can be called an ethnic community. Researchers believe that kinship ethnic groups are gradually becoming tribal communities. The tribe was an association of relatives who lived and worked together and played an important role in the early stages of the ethnic formation of certain peoples. and the roots of this layer are very ancient, as evidenced by archeological data.

According to researchers, by the Bronze Age in the southern regions of Central Asia were distributed representatives of the tall, narrow-faced race. The northern steppes and deserts were inhabited by tribes with a round head, a very wide face and a short face, which differed from the population of the south. In science, people with a southern appearance are called members of the Mediterranean race. They are spread over a large geographical area, such as Old Asia, Mesopotamia, Iran, Afghanistan, Central Asia, India. Northern-looking people are scattered from southern Siberia to Kazakhstan, in the north-eastern part of Central Asia to the Urals

and the Volga region. According to Sagdullayev's research, by the Bronze Age, the process of joining the ancient southern and northern peoples in Central Asia began, and it was during this period that the Bronze Age tribes living in our country became part of the ancient peoples of Central Asia. founders. This period is explained by the complex ethno-cultural processes that took place in the regions of our country. In particular, while the fertile plagues in the southern regions have begun to be absorbed by the settled agricultural population, the northern regions have begun to spread nomadic pastoral tribes. Socio-economic and cultural-ethnic processes are developing on the basis of the organic relations of nomadic pastoralists and sedentary population. Later, on the basis of this language, the literary Turkic language was formed, which Mahmud Qashqari called "the most open and fluent language". A number of works were written in the Turkic language during the IX-XII centuries, including Ahmad Yugnaki's (775-869) epic "Hibatul haqoyiq" (Gift of Truths), Yusuf Khos Khojib's (XI century), "Kutadg'u bilik" Among them are the works of Ahmad Yassavi (1041-1167) "Hikmatlar" and epics such as "Oguznoma", "Alpomish", "Gorugli". From the 10th century onwards, the Zlash people began to call themselves "Tajiks". The next dynasty after the Samanids and Qarakhanids (from the middle of the IX century to 1213), the Ghaznavids; 997-187), Seljuks (1040-1147), Khorezmshah-Anushtegens (1097-231) all belonged to the Turkic people and at one time had a dominant position not only in Central Asia but also in the Middle East. Iganlar. Although the Mongol invasion caused severe losses and losses to the population, researchers believe that the ethnogenesis and racial impact of the Uzbek people did not have a significant impact. Some groups of researchers connect the origin of this ethnonym with the name of the Golden Horde khan Uzbekkhan (1312-1341). Another group of researchers denies this idea: "The name" Uzbek "belongs to the Turkic tribes that lived in the White Horde region before Uzbekkhan, in its western Siberia and Kazakhstan (it may be derived from the names of khan tribes), put forward the idea that.

Some researchers derive the term "Uzbek" from the word "self", "independent" in the XII-XIV centuries. It is believed that the Uzbek, Turkmen,

Kazakh, Karakalpak peoples appeared at the same time, depending on the period of their origin. These peoples have lived in the areas where they now live for thousands of years. But at that time it was not yet called by its present name, and it was not said by its names. They were collectively called "Turks" or, after all, by the names of their tribes. In ancient times, the population was often called by the name of the place where they lived. changes. In particular, the Turkic population living in the Dashti Kipchak region came to the lands of Movarounnahr and merged with the settled population living here, and the population was called "Uzbek". In medieval historical literature, the name is also used as "Uzbek", "Uzbeks". But what is clear is that the Turkic tribes from the Dashti Kipchak region did not significantly influence the ethnogenesis, customs and traditions of the local population. On the contrary, they were influenced by high-level culture. According to the researcher A. Ibragimov, the Uzbek people are mainly composed of two ethnic groups. The first layers were formed in the Turan-Turkestan region. The second layer is formed in the areas from the banks of the Volga (Itil) to the north of Khorezm, the middle and lower reaches of the Syrdarya. In the past, this place was called by various names, including Dashti Kipchak, the Golden Horde, the Uzbek region, the Uzbek country, the Uzbek nation. This layer of our people can be called the northern layer.

In short, the basis of the Uzbek people were the local Saks, Massagets, Sogdians, Bakhtars, Khorezmians, Kanglis, Dovans, Chachs who lived in the territory of modern Uzbekistan for thousands of years. Although the alien population partially affected the local population, it did not radically change its genetics.

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